

PSYCHOLOGICAL IMPORTANCE OF THE CULTURE OF BEHAVIOR OF EMPLOYEES OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES.

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Abstract: In the protection of human rights in the internal affairs bodies, detailed information is given about the objects of interaction with the population, the culture of interaction, and the establishment of psychological relations.

Key words: objects of communication, culture of communication, psychological communication, upbringing, behavior, oral speech, speech style, social relations, literary style, upbringing, psychological characteristics.

Аннотация: При защите прав человека в органах внутренних дел дается подробная информация об объектах взаимодействия с населением, культуре взаимодействия, установлении психологических отношений.

Ключевые слова: объекты общения, культура общения, психологическое общение, воспитание, поведение, устная речь, стиль речи, общественные отношения, литературный стиль, воспитание, психологические особенности.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in his congratulatory speech on the day of the professional holiday of the internal affairs bodies, said that "In the new Uzbekistan, the employees of the internal affairs system serve as a strong support of our state and society in the successful implementation of our reforms based on the noble principle of "for the dignity of man". [1] This, in turn, encourages each employee to be courteous throughout their work and interactions with the public.

Employees of the internal affairs bodies deal with different strata of the population while performing their duties. It is known that behavior is a necessary and general condition for the activity of any person, society, an important factor of all-round development, and one of the criteria that separates a conscious person from nature. Therefore, the interactions of the employees of internal affairs bodies with the population have their own object and subject.

The objects of interaction with the population in the activities of the employees of the internal affairs bodies are as follows:

offenders who encroached on the freedom, dignity, life and property of citizens, as well as state and public property;

heads and officials of organizations, enterprises, institutions who violated labor and financial discipline;

families prone to breaking law and order and neglected;

victims, witnesses, impartial;

those who actively contribute to law enforcement, crime prevention and detection;

those who have no connection with the violation of the law, but apply for their personal affairs, that is, to obtain a passport, a driver's license or a permit to travel abroad;

foreign citizens applying for various issues.

The culture of dealings of internal affairs officers with the population is their interaction

with individuals, families, labor teams, social groups, various public and state organizations, institutions, and citizens of foreign countries, as well as moral and legal norms and principles in laws, decrees, regulations and orders. it refers to the system of regulated moral-aesthetic, legal relations. [2]

The communication of the employees of the internal affairs bodies includes the following:

- 1) orientation to the performance of a direct professional task;
- 2) legal regulation;
- 3) existence of a special object;
- 4) presence of psychological barriers;
- 5) knowledge of tattoos and slang, which are the special language of criminals, etc.

Any communication always includes the process of adaptation of the object and the subject.

Oral speech is expressed in colloquial and literary styles.

Speaking style refers to the way people communicate in dialects and dialects in everyday life. The rules and norms of speech culture are not strictly applied in the style of conversation. Nowadays, the inhabitants of our country speak many dialects, such as Tashkent, Fergana, Namangan, Andijan, Karshi, Surkhandarya, Bukhara, Samarkand.

Literary style refers to a style based on strict adherence to literary language norms. When speaking in a literary style, when giving a lecture, when holding official meetings, the rules of the language are fully observed.

Oral speech is more comprehensive than written speech and has the following characteristics:

- 1) the influence of dialect is strong in oral speech;
- 2) it is less possible to think in oral speech as in written speech;
- 3) oral speech has its own grammatical structure, construction order;
- 4) pronunciation, tone, gestures play an important role in oral speech;
- 5) the emergence of oral speech depends on the mood of the speaker, the situation in which the speech is being delivered, the normality and health of the speaker's speech organs;
- 6) it is very difficult to notice, record, teach and learn all the features of oral speech norms;
- 7) oral speech as a whole phenomenon (text) is an infinite and countless personal (individual) activity, many of its aspects take place on their own under different circumstances and disappear unnoticed;
- 8) when a person speaks, he does not pay enough attention to his speech as when he writes.

Speech and thinking are closely related processes, because after hearing the words of others, there is a need to think based on their meaning, and we express our thoughts through speech. [3]

Our feelings (emotional experiences) through oral speech are clearly manifested in the images, tone, rhyme, questions, silence between words, especially intonation.

For example, when a person's name is mentioned, different emotions and attitudes towards this person are aroused: a person deliberately expresses mental states such as love, anger, fear, hatred, pride in his facial expressions (depending on the type of mental process, temperament) or unintentionally expresses.

Depending on the physiological changes in a person's appearance, one can come to a certain opinion about the person's dominant thoughts, feelings, and relationships, and in the case of women, looking at cosmetics, clothes, and shoes. [4]

It is known that there must be certain grounds for preventive registration of a person, and in the presence of these grounds, the inspector of prevention must place a person on preventive registration within ten days (in the case of persons released from penal institutions, three days from the day they arrived at their place of residence). issues a decision in this regard and approves this decision by the head of the district, city internal affairs department, department. The approved decision shall be announced to the preventively registered person within three days (if he is not at his place of residence, three days from the moment his whereabouts were determined), he will introduce his rights and obligations and sign it, and from this day the person will be considered preventively registered. , will be in preventive account for one year. Naturally, during this period, the prevention inspector will have to carry out educational activities with the persons considered for prevention, and he will face various obstacles in the process of communication in order to establish a psychological relationship.

Employees of the internal affairs bodies come across obstacles in educational processes when they are taking preventive measures with teenagers who are difficult to educate, unhealthy families and persons with previous convictions. [5]

Establishing psychological communication is a goal-oriented, planned activity aimed at creating conditions that ensure the development of communication in the desired direction and the achievement of the specified goal.

The mental contact that internal affairs officers establish with citizens during the performance of their duties is an important indicator of their activity, and it is very different from the mental contact that people establish in their daily life. The main difference of psychological contact from the instructions specified in a number of normative documents regulating the service activities of preventive inspectors is that the successful entry of employees into psychological contact ultimately leads to obtaining important information and resisting behavior of citizens - to help, from indifference - closely related to the change to cooperation.

Today, the main goal of preventive accounting by the internal affairs bodies is the formation of socially positive behavior in persons with antisocial behavior, prone to committing offenses, and those who have committed offenses through individual, i.e. individual implementation of crime prevention on the basis of current laws. , based on their individual characteristics (knowledge, abilities, interests, needs), it consists of giving them the right direction, helping them to acquire a profession, encouraging them to engage in useful work, sports, etc. Therefore, every prevention inspector should have sufficient psychological knowledge when communicating with this category of persons.

Prophylactic inspectors conduct a preventive assessment of the following offenders, and psychological factors are taken into account in communication with them: [6]

Transaction is a very complex process, which consists of the sum of economic, political, legal, socio-spiritual relations and connections between people. The internal and external characteristics of all types of culture are embodied in communication. Therefore, it ensures the harmony and commonality of the internal and external culture of the employees of the formation offices at the level of historical succession and requirements. [7]

There are many forms of the culture of dealing with the population of the employees of the internal affairs bodies, among them three stand out:

- 1) behavioral culture;
- 2) appearance culture;

3) speech culture.

All these forms of communication culture are simultaneously felt in each person in the form of internal content and essence, external expression and their commonality or non-commonality. Therefore, the culture of behavior consists of three components:

- 1) the inner content and essence of character;
- 2) external expression of behavior;
- 3) degrees of harmony and proportion between them.

The internal content and essence of the behavior is the level of development of the moral-legal and aesthetic consciousness of the person, and the external appearance is determined by the aesthetic taste, understanding, which is their synthesis. The harmony and commonality of both shows that the employees of the Internal Affairs bodies have a high culture. That is why the code of ethics of the employees of the internal affairs bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan requires that the employee of the internal affairs bodies be of high culture, his high level of education, his ability to go beyond his word, his selflessness, his ability to perform his work on time, carefully and quickly, and the incident that occurred. It is determined by the fact that they have qualities such as clear analysis and correct decision-making, self-control, bravery, not to be deterred from various dangers and insults, and striving to be an example to their relatives, children and neighbors with their personal behavior and reputation.

Compliance with the above-mentioned requirements will, firstly, facilitate the solution of any complex issue, and secondly, it will have a positive effect on those around. [8]

Our great ancestors developed general rules of etiquette and culture based on their life experience. It is natural that these rules are an integral part of the interaction of each employee of Internal Affairs bodies with the population.

General rules of the culture of interaction. The general rules of the culture of interaction are as follows:

1. All goals will be fulfilled, closed doors will be opened from polite and careful handling. Kind words bring joy to the heart. An open face and sweet words are proof of friendship and love. Therefore, treat everyone with respect, be open-faced and sweet-spoken.
2. Do not talk to anyone when you are upset about something, be patient until your anger subsides. Forgive people's shortcomings, do not forget to think and pay attention in everything.
3. Don't stay away from people. Whoever you meet, don't kiss and become friends immediately without checking, be free-minded, speak the right words in everything, let your tongue and heart be the same.
4. Respond to the behavior of rude people with good behavior. Make sure that your treatment of people goes above and beyond what you expect from them.
5. Do not humiliate those who are younger than you, do not brag about your intelligence and career, but understand your career and the careers of others and treat everyone as they deserve.
6. If you want your interlocutor to treat you well, first treat him well yourself: don't say, "If people don't like me, let them not like me, what's wrong with me", but look for ways to be friends with them, because you are loving people, your maturity will not be wasted.
7. Speak good things to people, hide bad things. Treat people in such a way that they love you while you are alive and remember and mourn you after your death.
8. It is possible to ask for help from the people only when it becomes very necessary, at other times it is not right to be a burden on the people. Therefore, do not put your burden on the

people, do not be greedy for their wealth, work for yourself, work hard, create your livelihood with your own work.

9. Have you decided to do something, keep your word, keep your promise. Be loyal to whoever you are friends with. Rejoice at people's joys, grieve at their sorrows. Don't impose on others what you don't like. [9]

To sum up the above, the most important thing in our honorable profession is how we behave and present ourselves in front of others. we need to clearly convey the essence of all actions.

In short, treating citizens with intelligence, that is, sensitivity, listening to their pain, answering their questions sweetly, extending a helping hand to them, and treating them well in general will ultimately help to solve all difficult problems. This will further increase the reputation of the employees of the internal affairs bodies among the population and become a reliable support of the people.

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